

NGO's Perspectives in the management of cattle rustling among Pastoral Communities in Kenya

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Abstract: The research study focused on the support/effort made by NGO's in the management of cattle rustling among pastoral communities in Kenya. The general objective was the evaluation of the interface between state and non-state policies in managing cattle rustling among pastoral communities in Kenya. The specific objective was to establish the effect of NGO-based policies in the management of cattle rustling in Kenya. The area of study was in the Northern Western part of Kenya comprising five counties; Turkana, Baringo, Samburu, West Pokot and Elgeiyo Marakwet. The total population in this area under focus in terms of people was 2980,035. This was according to the National population census report of 2019. The sample size was 444 determined by use of Krejcie, R.V and Morgan D.W, table. The findings show that the NGO's provided employment to some students after school in the area of study at a mean score of 2.6 supported local residents to access loans to help them build structures at a mean score of 2.5, provided local residents with ready market for their produce at a mean score of 2.3 and encouraged inter community marriages as one way to discourage relatives from cattle theft at a mean of 1.0, mitigated cattle theft through peace rally's interventions at a mean score of 2.0, discourage cattle theft by dissuading the moran's from the practice at a mean score of 1.6 and provided local residents with farm implements at a mean score of 2.1, offered education on good farming technologies at a mean score of 1.4 while at the same time supporting education of school going children through bursaries at a mean score of 1.1. From the foregoing statistical findings it was imperative to advise the government of Kenya to involve and partner with NGO in her management strategies geared towards containment of cattle rustling among pastoral communities in Kenya. The NGO'S touched key elements instructions which could fast-track economic transformation hence enabling the pastoral communities to embrace agriculture and education and slowly abandon retrogressive cattle rustling practices altogether. The encouragement of inter-marriages and sedentary settlement are precursors to serious farming of livelihood crops geared towards socio-economic transformation.

Keywords: Cattle rustling, NGO's, policies, interface, management and pastoral communities.

1. INTRODUCTION

The practice of cattle rustling has over the years remained a prevalent activity pitying young males commonly known as 'morans' in the northern part of Kenya. The same practice is however witnessed in other parts of the world: Wild West, West Africa and South Africa. (Anderson, J.2021). In the Kenyan context, the early regimes of government during development administration denied policy researchers. Academic and universities permission to find out the real causes and provide solutions exacerbated the glaring inequalities in the economy brought about by cattle rustling in pastoral communities. (Stone, 2008). According to Metivier, (2022), cattle rustling practice alienated the pastoral communities from mainstream economic development of Kenya hence ostracising the region from much needed modern civilization experienced in the regions such as central and western parts of the country. In other developed jurisdictions, such as Canada,

South Africa and South America, criminal procedure codes had been put in place to deal with cattle rustling. The suspects faced death penalties, prolonged jail terms and some got incapacitated. (Sharkansky et al., 1969). In the converse, the suspects of cattle rustling were never charged expeditiously due to either lack of concrete evidence, or weak and interfered with investigations. (Mukutu, 2019). The regional political organizations have had several mitigation measures including multi-lateral protocols to reduce thuggery and give room for NGO's policies of agricultural exploitation, educational support, water provisions and Gender Based Violence to transform communities. (G.O.K 2014) One such remarkable initiative was the Nairobi protocol on prevention, control and reduction of small arms and light weapons in the great lakes region and horn of Africa where leaders asked International Non-Governmental Organizations to support African Governments in such regions with the provision of funds and other economic mechanisms in agriculture and research as a means to empower the people to diversify their socio-economic livelihoods. (G.O.K 2005). Other initiatives have been encouraging formal learning through universal basic education and 100% transition of learners in all schools. In Agricultural sector, the clarion call has been modernization and upgrading of livestock, high breed seeds and creation of research institutions to facilitate ease of collaboration with NGO council for awareness among pastoral communities on the dangers of the effects of cattle rustling and chief among the collaboration policies was replacement of indigenous cattle breeds with exotic ones. (G.O.K 2019). The policies of NGO's such as world vision, Red Cross, Red Crescent and Action Aid corroborated well with those of the state in areas of education, agriculture, trade, cultural re-engineering and attitude change. (Kaimba, 2018).

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The cattle rustling menace in Kenya had assumed a pandemic status among pastoral communities in the Northern part region despite a myriad of mitigation measures. (Mkutu.K, 2019). According to Bashir (2021), in his research publication dubbed (re-engineering peace and security in East Africa.) observed that cattle rustling had brought about atrocities due to militarization of cattle rustlers. The situation on the ground among pastoral communities was characterized by massive relocation of people due to raids, useless and un-called for debts, desolate villages and social economic disorders where schools and markets were closed down. According to Cheserek et al... (2012), cattle rustling impoverished the pastoral communities in the study area. The cattle rustling activities were unstoppable in the North Rift due to the prevalence of gun culture which aided in the several raids for livestock occasioning untold sufferings ranging from loss of lives, massive displacement of populations, closure of schools and hospitals, a situation characterized by hopelessness and poverty despite the existence of elected leaders and security agencies. (Berilla et al... 2019). Many public policy and research academics have in the past presented to government and those in positions of authority with some research papers on cattle rustling but less has been achieved so far in the management of cattle rustling. It was due to this state of affairs that the NGO's came up with socio-economic policies to augment state policies in cattle rustling menace and their main message to government was to have close working collaboration to stamp out the menace.

Objective of the study

To find out the effect of NGO's policies in the management of cattle rustling among pastoral communities in Kenya

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The NGO's have their policies spread around socio-economic empowerment of communities affected by poverty, wars and conflicts which deprive them of human dignity. (Goodland, J.2011). The researcher deployed structural functionalism and conflict transformation theories to highlight the NGO's policies in the management of cattle rustling. The structural functionalism theory illustrated the inter-connectedness of institutions, roles, norms and cultural practices in supportive web. (Britannia, 2021). The weakening of one social order and structure which supports peoples' livelihoods substantially affects other socio-economic livelihood mechanisms. (Mohammed, 2016). This theory corroborated very well with the circumstances on the ground because the education sector, agricultural sector and general good in the social fabric crumbled down due to failure by security sector to tame insecurity incidences brought about by cattle rustling. (Kratli, 2011). According to Mkutu, (2019), cattle rustling practices had however undergone several phases of transformation by 2000 compared to the period before and immediately after independence in Kenya. He observed that the introduction of 'gun' into the scene replacing bows, arrows spears and shields, made the situation worse. On the same breath (Bravery, 2015) observed that the Europeans had brought the gun and ammunitions to pacify African resistance and subjugate them to their advantage only to be an imperative in cattle rustling. According to Okoli, (2020) cattle rustling had undergone tremendous

transformation to the extent that political clans embraced it for economic gains. The author however has been working under the sleeves to discourage cattle rustling (Kaimba, 2018). He observed that a large number of players joined raiders, politicians and meat consumers in urban centres and cities through NGO's, remained focused, encouraging local residents to embrace alternative sources of livelihood. (Okumu, 2020). The Non-Governmental Organizations were drawn into salvaging the deterioration Human Rights situations, closure of sunroofs after raiding, destruction of health centres and general misery of innocent local residents. (Miall, 1999). The states stabilization policies and strategies deployed to bring order and peace were dehumanizing, lacked observation of human rights and caused a lot of misery to innocent civilians. (Okoli, 2020). The NGO's had commanded high level of respect and acceptance from the local people than government officers who were considered ruthless and clueless on how to tame cattle rustling. (Karanja, 2017). The NGO's provided many socio-economic change fronts which were geared towards improvement of education, land range management, agricultural improvements and cultural change. (Onyango, 2017).

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher deployed simple random sampling, purposive sampling and observation methods to collect data. He further utilized mixed study design approach where quantitative data from questionnaires and qualitative from interview schedules data were analysed. The total population in this area under focus in terms of people was 2980,035. This was according to the National population census report Of 2019. The sample size was 444 determined by use of Krejcie, R.V and Morgan D.W, table. The findings were arrived at by use of software package on social sciences as a tool of analysis. The findings and results were displayed on the table below.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

NGOs	N	M	SD
Mitigates cattle rustling in our community	384	1.38	.3453
Supported agriculture in our community thus reducing cattle rustling	384	1.289	.4539
Encouraged changing traditions of cattle rustling in our community	384	1.414	.0361
Encourage education	384	1.138	.3453
Provides employment after school	384	2.567	.7230
Offers education on good farming	384	1.427	.4953
Offers locals market to their produce	384	2.278	.0285
Encourages community intermarriages	384	1.00	.0021
Teaching that cattle rustling is not the only means of paying dowry	384	1.289	.4539
Supports local loans to own permanent structures	384	2.56	.2938
Favour other communities	384	1.415	.0361
Discourage cattle rustling	384	1.557	.7329
Supports cattle rustling victims with food and settlements	384	1.419	.4940
Gives scholarship	384	1.992	.1906
Supports locals to own farm implements	384	2.119	.3543
Teach against killing to acquire cattle	384	1.419	.4940
Mitigate peace among communities	384	1.997	.7630
Have increased in our region	384	1.851	.8310

The results from quantitative analysis whose sample size was N (384), indicated the following: The NGOs discouraged cattle rustling in all of their policy programs and were able to achieve a mean score of 1.6 while they scored a mean score of 2 in their support of education through provision of scholarship. In respect to provision of employment to school leavers, they achieved a mean score of 2.6. and a mean score of 2.1 in provision of farm implements. They also achieved a mean score of 2.3 in provision of markets to the local peoples' farm produce while mitigation against cattle rustling was also in the agenda. However, the NGOs did not do well in a number of policy initiatives such as teaching that cattle was not the only source of livelihood to provide dowry (1.3) ; parents to ensure that their children embraced education (1.1) ; encouraged change from cattle rustling and other forms of cultural practices to promote inter-community marriages. The results from qualitative analysis indicated as follows: from a sample size of N (60). The local residents agreed in their

interview schedules that the NGOs managed cattle rustling menace in 4 main ways, namely; Provision of alternative sources of livelihoods, organized livestock watering and grazing patterns, improved range land management and also achieved realization of peace through peace dialogues and conflict resolution.

6. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECCOMENDATIONS

SUMMARY

The study found out that NGOs rarely mitigated cattle rustling in the study area. The NGOs had rarely supported agriculture in their community thus reducing cattle rustling. The NGOs had rarely encouraged changing the tradition of cattle rustling in the community. On the contrary, the respondents disagreed that NGOs practiced unfairness among communities. Through non-governmental policies, peace and stability had been enhanced. The non-governmental fund had helped cattle farmers to regain momentum through funding and offered aid to large scale and small scale farmers. The NGOs rarely encouraged education, nor supported victims of cattle rustling for food and settlements. The NGOs rarely gave scholarships to learners. The NGOs sometimes provided employment to students after school. The NGOs sometimes supported local people with loans to own permanent structures. The NGOs sometimes supported local residents to own farm implements. The NGOs offered education on good farming. The NGOs sometimes offered local community markets for their produce. The respondents disagreed that the NGOs encouraged community intermarriages. The NGOs rarely taught against killing of people to acquire cattle. The NGOs rarely taught that cattle theft was not the only means through which dowry was paid. The NGOs sometimes mitigated against cattle rustling among communities. Finally, NGOs had increased in the region as far as residents were concerned. The effect of NGO policies in the management of cattle rustling achieved several milestones in shaping the socio-cultural lives of the pastoral communities in the North Rift. The communities appreciated the NGO engagement strategies and were able to mingle freely unlike government agencies who were mandated to stabilize security and end lawlessness brought about by cattle rustling. The NGOs supported key socio-economic sectors; Agriculture, Education and Cultural Integration through peaceful means. They never coerced the locals to change their way of life but did it through dialogue and instructions.

CONCLUSION

The study results indicated that the NGO policies in agriculture, education and cultural transformation managed to tame cattle rustling menace amid other strategies put in place by Kenyan government which the communities did not fully embrace because they termed them insensitive to their obtaining situations. From the study, it was discovered that NGOs had succeeded in providing livelihood support through provision of farm implements and loans to enable the people to put up permanent residences which had tremendously changed their ways of lives from informal structures to sedentary type of settlements. This had a great impact in pastoralism as recorded from the interviewees. Just like the faith based policies the NGOs had supported the local people in three ways; provision of jobs to the youth once they complete school, soft loans to start alternative forms of business engagements and also encouraged the local people to engage in agricultural farming of drought resistant crops to withstand harsh climatic conditions pronounced in the semi-arid areas in the North Rift. The NGOs socio-economic transformation policies though not phenomenal, augmented government strategies which were able to make pastoral communities of the North Rift improve their livelihoods. It is both notable and remarkable that the government involvement in management of cattle rustling had achieved some level of success while complimented by NGOs policy initiatives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, it was apparent that NGOs supported community dialogues and intermarriages which were critical in ensuring that there was cohesion amongst communities. They also taught against using stolen animals to pay dowry which was a positive attribute in managing cattle rustling. For the case of individual based policies, community role modeling was a critical factor that discouraged young people from engaging in cattle rustling. It was very clear that cattle rustling became vicious and high just before elections and during campaigns for political reasons and from table 4.10 it was clear that cattle rustling was not liked by many and was therefore a practice which could easily be stopped if given due attention. The government of Kenya should marshal together other cattle rustling management players in the North Rift with a view to coming up with a deliberate plan choreographed to stamp out the long-lasting menace once and for all. The plan should bring players on board and synthesize their policy actions to concretize and strengthen the fight against cattle rustling. The plan should put NGOs operatives at the fore front because the communities listen to them more than government

functionaries. The socio-economic transformation agenda among players should concentrate more in the opening up of the area under study by increased infrastructural facilities such as roads, police stations, schools and hospitals and most importantly invest in bringing about cultural and attitude change with a view to facing out cattle rustling support systems such as moranism, and payment of dowry by use of stolen livestock. The security agencies of government should work closely with NGOs to ensure 100% transition of learners among the pastoral communities in the North Rift while supporting alternative sources of livelihood which would act as a fall back plan by those abandoning cattle rustling. The government should work closely with the NGOs involved in peace and security with clear visions and missions to manage cattle rustling. Such collaborations should be in the field of education and research, agriculture and innovation, peace and security programmes and best practices in range management. This means that the NGOs should have deliberate workable legal framework with the Government with special bias to managing cattle rustling in the North Rift.

REFERENCES

- [1] Anderson, J.; Gauthier, M; Thomas, G. & Wondolleck, J. (1996). Setting the stage. Presented at the Global e-Conference on Addressing Natural Resource Conflict Through Community Forestry, (Jan -Apr 1996). Forests, Trees and People Programme of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy.
- [2] Appadorai, A. (2004). *The Substance of Politics*, (4th ed). New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- [3] Azar, E. E. (1990). *The Management of Protracted Social*. London: Dartmouth Publishing Company
- [4] Barilla S., Plang I. & Isaac J. (2019). The state, policies and cattle rustling. *Scientific Research Journal (SCIRJ)*, VII(III), March 2019.
- [5] Barrett, C., Chabari, D., & Coppock, D. (2003). Livestock pricing in the Northern Kenya Rangelands. *Journal of African Economies*. 12(2), 127-155.
- [6] Buchanan-Smith, M & Lind, J. (2005). *Armed violence and poverty in Northern Kenya: a case study for the Armed Violence and Poverty Initiative*. Bradford: Centre for International Cooperation and Security/Bradford University.
- [7] Bunei, E. K., McElwee, G., & Smith, R. (2016). From bush to butchery: cattle rustling as an entrepreneurial process in Kenya. *Society and Business Review*, 11(1), 46-61.
- [8] Campbell, I. Dalrymple, S., Rob, C. & Crawford, A. (2009). *Climate change and conflict – lessons from community conservancies in northern Kenya*. Winnipeg: International Institute for Sustainable Development.
- [9] Cheruiyot, L. & Sabala, K. (2008). *Human Security and the Control of Small Arms in Mwagiru*, M. (Ed) Human Nairobi, Nairobi: Africa Peace Forum.
- [10] Cheserek, G.J., Omondi, A. & Odenyo, V. (2012). *Nature and Causes of Cattle Rustling among Some Pastoral Communities in Kenya*. Eldoret: Chepkoilel University College.
- [11] Floyd, K. (2017). *Human Communication: A Critical Reader (Third Edition)*. New York: McGraw Hill Education LLC.
- [12] Frank, W. (2000). *Cattle thieves hit NSW farms*, Sydney: Morning Herald
- [13] Gakuria, A. R. (2013). *Natural resource based conflict among pastoralist communities in Kenya*, Unpublished PhD dissertation, Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- [14] Gallie, D. (2004). *Resisting Marginalization: Unemployment Experience and Social Policy in the European Union*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [15] Galtung, J. & Carl, G. J. (2000). *Searching for Peace*, London: Pluto.
- [16] Galtung, J. (1969). *Conflict as a way of life*, “ in H. Freeman, *Progress in Mental Health*, London: J. & A. Churchill.
- [17] Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means*, London: Sage.
- [18] GoK (2005). *Draft ASAL Gender Policy Guidelines*. Nairobi: Government Printers.

- [19] GoK (2005). Sessional Paper No. 1 of 2005 on a Policy framework for education, training and Research. Nairobi: Government Printers.
- [20] GoK (2006). National policy for the sustainable development of arid and semi-arid lands of Kenya, Nairobi: Government Printers.
- [21] GoK (2007). Kenya Vision 2030. A globally competitive and prosperous Kenya. Nairobi: Government Printers.
- [22] Greiner, C. (2013). Guns, Land, and Votes: Cattle Rustling and the Politics of Boundary (re)Making in Northern Kenya. *African Affairs*, 112/447, 216– 237 Oxford University Press
- [23] Hendrick, D., Armon J & Mearns R (1998). The Changing Nature of Conflict and Famine Vulnerability: The Case of Livestock Raiding in Turkana District, Kenya. *Disasters*, 22 (3), 185-199.
- [24] Hendrickson, D, J. A., &Mearns, R. (1996). Livestock raiding among the pastoral Turkana of Kenya. Redistribution, predation and the links to famine. *Institute of Development Studies Bulletin* 27(3), 17-30.
- [25] Herskovits, M. J. (1926). The Cattle Complex in East Africa. *American Anthropologist New Series*, 28(1), 230-272
- [26] Kaimba, G. K., Njehia, B. K., & Guliye, A. Y. (2011). Effects of cattle rustling and household characteristics on migration decisions and herd size amongst pastoralists in Baringo District, Kenya. *Pastoralism: Research, Policy and Practice*, 1(1), 1-16.
- [27] Kenya Human Rights Commission (2010). *Morans No More the Changing Face of Cattle-Rustling in Kenya*, Nairobi: Kenya Human Rights Commission
- [28] Kenya Human Rights Commission (K.H.R.C.) (2001). *Raiding Democracy: The Slaughter of the Marakwet in the Kerio Valley*. Nairobi: Kenya Human Rights Commission.
- [29] Kenya Human Rights Commission [KHRC]. (1998). *Killing the Vote: State Sponsored Violence and Flawed Elections in Kenya*. Nairobi: KHCR Report.
- [30] Kenya National Human Rights Commission (KNCHR) (2017). *Mending the Rift: Public inquiry on insecurity and its impact on the enjoyment of Fundamental Human Rights in the North Rift Region of Kenya*. Nairobi: Kenya Human Rights Commission.
- [31] Khan, M. (1994). Market based early warning indicators of famine for the pastoral households of the Sahel. *World Development*, 22(2).
- [32] Kiprono, c. z. This paper analyses colonial and post-colonial evolution of cattle rustling in Tot and Tunyo divisions of Elgeyo Marakwet County 1900-2000.
- [33] KNBS, (2019). *Kenya Population and Housing Census: Volume I*. Nairobi: KNBS.
- [34] Knobloch, L. K. (2015). Uncertainty Reduction Theory. In *The International Encyclopedia of Interpersonal Communication* (pp1-9). Retrieved from <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118540190.wbeic144>
- [35] Krätli, S & Swift, J. (2003). *Understanding and managing pastoral conflict in Kenya*. Sussex: University of Sussex.
- [36] Krätli, S. (2001). Education provision to nomadic pastoralists a literature review. IDS Working Paper 126 MoE – Ministry of Education (2009). *Various Reports on Monitoring of mobile schools in Fafi, Lagdera, Wajir West, Wajir East, Ijara, Tana River, Tana Delta, Turkana North and Samburu East Districts*.
- [37] Krejcie, R.V., & Morgan, D.W., (1970). Determining Sample Size for Research Activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*. Retrieved from <https://www.everydaydemocracy.org/stories/creating-healthy-neighborhoods-through-active-and-policy-change>.
- [38] Kriesberg, L. (1998). *Constructive Conflicts: From Escalation to Resolution*. Lanham: Rowman and Littlefield.
- [39] Krippendorff, E. (1973). Peace Research and the Industrial Revolution, *Journal of Peace Research*, 10, 185-201.

- [40] Kuden, P. (2017) Cattle rustling and Socio-Economic Development of Mangu Local Government Area of Plateau State (2010-2016).
- [41] Kwaja, C. (2014). Blood, cattle, and cash: Cattle rustling and Nigeria' s burgeoning underground economy. *West African Insight*, 4(3), 1-6.
- [42] Kwaja, C. (2014). Policy Brief Review Responses to the Plateau State Government to Violence Conflicts in the State. *West African Insight*, 4(3), 1-6.
- [43] Lassance, A. (2021). What is a policy, and what is a government program? A simple question with no clear answer, until now. *Simetria*, 1(8), 140-148.
- [44] Le Ster, M. (2011). Conflicts over water around Lake Turkana; Volume IX, No. 3; French Institute for Research in Africa (IFRA); pp 1-4
- [45] Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*, Washington, D.C.: United States Institute of Peace Press.
- [46] Lederach, J.P. (1995). *Preparing for Peace: Conflict Transformation across Cultures*, New York: Syracuse University Press.
- [47] Leonhardt, M. (2000). *Conflict Impact Assessment of EU Development Cooperation with ACP Countries: A review of literature and practice*, London: International Alert/Saferworld.
- [48] Miall, H., Oliver R, & Tom, W. (1999). *Contemporary Conflict Resolution*, Cambridge: Polity.
- [49] Midley, O. (2012). Rural Crime on the Increase. *Farmers Guardian*: Retrieved from <http://www.farmersguardian.com/home/business/fg-investigation-reveals-rural-crime- picture/48790.article>
- [50] Mkutu, K. (2006). Small Arms and Light Weapons among Pastoralist Groups in the Kenya- Uganda Border Area. *African Affairs* 106(422), 47– 70.
- [51] Mkutu, K. (2006). Small Arms and Light Weapons among Pastoralist Groups in the Kenya- Uganda Boarder Area. *African Affairs* 106(422), 47– 70.
- [52] Mkutu, K., (2019). Pastoralists, politics and development projects. *Understanding the layers of armed conflict in Isiolo County, Kenya*. Nairobi: United States International University.
- [53] MoE Ministry of Education (2008). *Report on the Policy Framework for Nomadic Education in Kenya*, July 2008. Nairobi: Ministry of Education
- [54] MoE (2006). *Ministry of Education Strategic Plan 2006-2011*, Nairobi: Ministry of Education
- [55] MOEST (2005). *Kenya Education Sector Support Programme 2005-2010: Delivering quality education and training to all Kenyans*. Nairobi: MOEST
- [56] Mohammed, A.H (2006). *Closed to progress. An assessment of socio-economicc impact of conflict on pastoral and semi-pastoral communities in Kenya and Uganda*.
- [57] National Drought Management Authority (NDMA). (2012). *Common Programme Framework for Ending Drought Emergencies*, Nairobi: NDMA.
- [58] Ndambuki, M. (2016). *The Impact of Illicit Arms on Security: Case Study of Cattle Rustling in Northern Kenya* Unpublished PhD dissertation, Nairobi: University of Nairobi.
- [59] Republic of Kenya. (2013). *Sector Plan for Drought Risk Management and Ending Drought Emergencies. Second Medium Term Plan 2013-2017. Drought, Risk Management and Policy*. Retrieved from <https://www.ndma.go.ke/index.php/resource-center/policy-documents/send/44-policy-documents/4310-vision-2030-sector-plan-for-drought-risk-management-and-ed-2013-17>